

Thesis for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy

Molecular Characterization of Myosin
Light Chain 2 Gene (*mlc2f*) and
Recapitulation of its Expression Pattern
Using *mlc2f* Promoter-Driven
Transgenesis in Mud Loach
(*Misgurnus mizolepis*)

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Abstract

The fast skeletal myosin light chain2 gene (*mlc2f*) was isolated and characterized from mud loach (*Misgurnus mizolepis*). The mRNA expression of endogenous *mlc2f* in wild type adult mud loach was mainly observed in skeletal muscle tissue and much lower levels in skin and gill tissue. A transgenic construct using *mlc2f* promoter attached to cyan fluorescent protein gene was used to drive skeletal muscle-specific expression of the fluorescent reporter in transgenic mud loach . All transgenic founders exhibited mosaic expression of transgene. A founder transgenic male successfully transmitted the transgene to the subsequent generation. Transgenic CFP signals were not found during embryonic developmental stage but afterward the signals were found to be visualized at 12 hours post hatching. During early larval growth, CFP signals were observed in fin muscles, head muscles and skeletal muscles. At juvenile stage, CFP signals were observed reliably in skeletal muscle. In adult stage of F1 generation, strongest CFP expression was visible in skeletal muscle tissue in accordance with the highest mRNA expression of endogenous *mlc2f* in muscle. Fluorescent transgene was passed on to the subsequent generation (F2) following the Mendelian single gene inheritance pattern. Histological analysis using F2 transgenic also showed the skeletal muscle-dominant transgenic expression. This study provided evidence of the potential of

mlc2f promoter to drive skeletal muscle specific expression in the mud loach. Using *mlc2f* promoter and CFP as reporter gene, it is possible to monitor development of fast skeletal muscle in real time fashion and on site from larva until adult stage of transgenic mud loach.

I. INTRODUCTION

Muscles structure are made of bundles of muscle fibers. Every muscle fibers contains myofibrils which are structure of actin and myosin filaments organized into continuous repeating units called sarcomeres. A unit of sarcomere has an approximate length of 2.3 μm . Each sarcomeres are defined and separated by the Z disc (Cooper and Hausman, 2007). Myosin protein is one of the primary components of muscle tissue. Myosin collaborates with actin protein for the purpose of cell movement and converts the energy from ATP to generate force and cell movement, which is the most important feature for muscle contraction process (Alberts *et al.*, 2004; Cooper and Hausman, 2007).

Myosin molecules are systematically arranged to bipolar structures. Head of myosin molecules (thick filaments about 15 nm in diameter) extend from the surface of the structures and interact with adjacent actin (thin filament about 7 nm in diameter) to generate contractile force between thick and thin filaments. Myosin and actin are arranged parallel to each other. Muscle contraction involves an active sliding process between actin and myosin filaments. During muscle contraction, myosin and actin filaments repetitively slide past each other by nanometers. Both of the filaments themselves do not shorten and ATP is being cleaved during the process (Harrington and Rodgers, 1984).

There are several types of myosin in cell. Myosin of muscle is part of the myosin II subfamily. Myosin II structure consisted of a pair of identical myosin molecules (heavy chains about 200 kDa each) and two pairs of light chains (about 20 kDa each). Each heavy chains are made of a globular head at one end and a coiled long tail at the other end. Two light chains attached

at the neck of each head region (Weeds and Lowey, 1971; Harrington and Rodgers, 1984; Rayment *et al.*, 1993; Goldspink *et al.*, 2001; Alberts *et al.*, 2004; Cooper and Hausman, 2007)

Myosin heavy chains (MHC) can be divided into two groups: the sarcomeric (cardiac and skeletal) and non sarcomeric (smooth muscle and non muscle) myosin (England and Loughna, 2013). Sarcomeres structure showed the striated appearance of skeletal and cardiac muscle. Three myosin light chains have been identified by chromatography. Two of the light chains are chemically related and cannot be removed from myosin without loss of ATPase activity. Since these light chains are dissociated at pH of 11, and are essential for activity, they are termed alkali (essential) light chains. The third component can be removed from myosin by treatment of 5,5'-dithio-(bis-2-nitrobenzoic acid) or DTNB without deprivation of ATPase activity. It is termed DTNB (non essential) regulatory light chains (Weeds and Lowey, 1971). Based on amino acid sequence and crystal structure, essential light chain (ELC) and regulatory light chain (RLC) were belong to the superfamily of EF-hand proteins. Both light chains contain four EF-hand domain (Kretsinger and Wasserman, 1980)

Fish skeletal muscle myosins contain two alkali light chains (MLC1 and MLC3) and a regulatory (non essential) light chain (MLC2). Major difference between MLC2 and MLC1 is the existence of serine residue of MLC2 in the N-terminal of the peptide (England and Loughna, 2013). Different isoforms have been isolated and characterized from skeletal muscle of fish. Each isoforms have their unique contribution to muscle growth and regulation during development. Unlike mammals, fish undergoes skeletal muscle growth by

hyperplasia and hypertrophy throughout their life (Rowlerson *et al.*, 1995).

Energy consumption during swimming in water is not straightforwardly related to speed as in locomotion on land. The burst speed swimming required more energy than the sustained swimming. Fish muscle fibres are dominated by fibre types that can produce power rapidly. Majority (90%) of fish skeletal muscles are composed of anaerobic white fibres (fast twitch, large diameter) while around 0.5 - 29% are composed of the red fibres (slow twitch, thin diameter). Some fish species have muscle fibers composed of a narrow line of pink muscle, an intermediate between fast and slow muscle (Johnston, 1981)

Fish is a popular model for transgenesis study. The number of fish species is vast and fish inhabits different ecological niche. Several methods have been used for gene transfer. Microinjection by puncturing the egg membrane, pore formation by exposure to high voltage, multiple membrane puncture by microprojectiles or charge interactions between DNA/lipid and membrane are several known method for gene transfer in fish. The most common method for fish transgenesis is microinjection. Microinjection precisely transfers DNA into individual eggs or embryos (Sin, 1997).

Due to their nature of external fertilization, fish embryos are abundant and can be collected easily for genetic manipulation at any stages of development (Maclean *et al.*, 1987; Houdebine and Chourrot, 1991). Despite the advantages, pronucleus of fish is not visible and foreign gene could be injected only to cytoplasm of animal pole. Integration of foreign gene can be delayed until gastrula or even later, resulting in multi-sited integration and mosaicism (Yan and Sun, 2000). In some species, embryos develop immediately after fertilization and the first cell stage is too short to allow gene transfer

(Houdebine and Chourrot, 1991).

The first step of production of transgenic fish is construction of artificial genes. Later, the gene is transferred into fish eggs or embryos. While developing, the embryo, fry or adult will be analyzed for the presence of transgene. After identification, transgenic fish can be crossed with wild type fish to check the germline transmission rate to its progeny (Sin, 1997).

Mud loach, *Misgurnus mizolepis* Günther is a freshwater fish, a member of family Cobitidae which is known to be distributed in Korea and China (Kim *et al.*, 1987). During spawning, they laid demersal, adhesive, light yellow eggs with an average diameter of 1.1 mm. Hatching occurred about 24 hours after fertilization. This species has several attractive traits as experimental model fish such as: small body size, fast growth rate, fast embryonic development and short generation time (Nam *et al.*, 1996; Nam *et al.*, 2000). Several transgenesis study have successfully been conducted with this species (Nam *et al.*, 1996; Nam *et al.*, 1999; Nam *et al.*, 2000, Nam *et al.*, 2004).

Fluorescent protein was first discovered from jellyfish *Aequorea victoria* almost 70 years ago. It was not gain much attention until successful cloning and heterologous expression. Immediately, green fluorescent protein (GFP) became popular for cell and molecular biology study (Chudakov *et al.*, 2005) GFP and its blue, cyan, and yellow mutation and several others fluorescent protein discovered from marine anthozoa provide extensive selection of colors for biological imaging (Matz *et al.*, 1999; Shaner *et al.*, 2005; Erard *et al.*, 2013). Each fluorescent protein has different brightness, structure and chemical properties (Matz *et al.*, 1999; Shaner *et al.*, 2005; Guyon *et al.*, 2013). However, several fluorescent protein exhibit photoinstability (Finley *et al.*,

2001). Each researcher should evaluate available fluorescent protein that compatible with their experiments (Shaner *et al.*, 2005)

AmCyan1 is a mutation of fluorescent protein amFP486 clone from the sea anemone *Anemonia majano*. AmCyan has a peak excitation at 458 nm and emission peak of 489 (Matz *et al.*, 1999; Gurvey *et al.*, 2012). Applications of AmCyan1 have already been reported for tissue specific expression in fish (Vu *et al.*, 2014) and in cell labelling (Gurvey *et al.*, 2012).

The purposes of this study were to characterize the mud loach *mlc2f* gene at molecular level and to evaluate the potentials of *mlc2f* promoter to drive expression in skeletal muscle. This study aimed to demonstrate the potential of *mlc2f* promoter-driven transgenesis and to visualize fast skeletal muscle development during life cycle of mud loach.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Isolation and cloning of *mlc2f* gene from mud loach

The cDNA encoding mud loach *mlc2f* was found from express sequence tag (EST) of whole body cDNA library. Complete cDNA was isolated using vectorette PCR amplification and the full-length sequence was confirmed by sequence analysis of RT-PCR product.

Deduced amino acid sequence of mud loach *mlc2f* can be assessed under the accession number KX347548. A two round genome walking to 5'-direction are performed using Universal GenomeWalker Kit (Clontech Laboratories, Mountain View, CA, USA).

Oligonucleotide primers that were used during genome walking PCR were MM gMLC2 GW1 (5'-CATGTTAAGACGGTATACGTGAAGTC-3'), MM gMLC2 GW2 (5'-AAGAAGCTCAAGAAGCGAAGATGGTG-3'), MM gMLC2 GW3 (5'-GATGGGACGCTATTCTCGTATCGCT-3') and MM gMLC2 GW4 (5'-TGTCGGCATCGTCTATTCTGCTGTCC-3'). Upon completion of genome walking PCR, a 3002 bp upstream sequence from ATG initiation codon was assembled in contig using the sequence analysis software Sequencher (Gene Codes Corp., Ann Arbor, MI, USA).

Based on the 5'-upstream sequence and cDNA sequence, a continuous fragment spanning from the 5'-end of regulatory region to the 3'-untranslated region (UTR) of *mlc2f* gene was PCR-isolated again for determining the representative genomic sequence.

The amplified product were cloned to pGEM T-easy vector (Promega, Madison, WI, USA) and multiple recombination clones (n = 6) possessing the correct insert size were sequenced at both directions. Genomic sequence of mud loach *mlc2f* including its 5'-flanking region was registered to GenBank under the accession number KX347547.

2.2 Bioinformatics analysis

2.2.1. Genomic organization

Genomic organization of deduced polypeptide of mud loach myosin light chain 2 (*mlc2*) were compared with those of previously known vertebrate orthologues compiled from the public databases including the GenBank. We also analyze genomic information of putative *mlc2f* (*mylpf*) by Ensembl Genome Browser (<http://www.ensembl.org/index.html>)

2.2.2. Phylogenetic analysis

The *mlc2f* genes of several teleosts were assembled from the GenBank and Ensembl Genome Browser. Multiple sequence alignment was carried out at the nucleotide level (coding nucleotide sequence) using Clustal Omega (<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/Tools/msa/clustalo/>). Nucleotide matrix of *mlc2f* genes was used for the phylogenetic analysis. Slow cardiac myosin regulatory chain 2 (*myl2*) genes were used as outgroups. The nucleotide sequence data were subjected to neighbor-joining (NJ) analysis in MEGA 7 (Kumar *et al.*, 2016). The phylogenetic tree was reconstructed using the Poisson model. Robustness of tree topologies was evaluated by bootstrap analysis with 1,000 replicates.

2.3. Expression analysis of *mlc2f* in adult tissues

Quantitative real-time RT-PCR was performed to examine the tissue distribution pattern of the *mlc2f* mRNAs with the total RNAs isolated from brain, eye, fin, gill, intestine, kidney, liver, muscle and skin. Total RNA was prepared from fish aged 11 months. Total RNA was extracted from samples using RNeasy Plus Mini Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) according to the manufacturer's instruction including the DNase treatment step.

Reverse transcription (RT) using an aliquot of total RNA (3 µg) was carried out using Omniscript Reverse Transcription Kit (Qiagen) according to the manufacturer's manual. During the RT reaction, the normalization control was prepared by the inclusion of mud loach 18S rRNA primer (5'-CAAGAATTTACCTCTAGCGGC-3').

In order to optimize the PCR conditions, *mlc2f* mRNA segments were amplified using the following primers (MM MLC2f c1F: 5'-AGTTTCTCAGCAGAGGAGAT-3' and MM MLC2f c1R: 5'-AGAGTAAAGCAGCGAGGGAT-3'). Normalization control 18S rRNA fragment was also amplified with following primers (MM18S rRNA 1F: 5'-TGAGAAACGGCTACCACATC-3' and MM18S rRNA 1R: 5'-CCATGGGTTTAGGATACGCT-3'). PCR amplification was carried out using an iCycler® Real-Time Optical Module (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA) and iQ™ SYBR® Green Supermix (Bio-Rad).

2.4. Preparation of fluorescent reporter vector

Heterologous expression assay of mud loach *mlc2f* promoter was performed

by constructing a cyan fluorescent protein (cfp)-mediated reporter vector. The 3-kb upstream fragment of the mud loach *mlc2f* was PCR amplified using primers (MM MLC2 pFW2: 5'-ATTGTCGACTAGTCCTGCCTTTAGCTAA-3' and MM MLC2 pRV2: 5'-ATTACCGGTGTTAAGACGGTATACGTGA-3') of which 5'-ends were modified to contain additional sequences for *SalI* and *AgeI* sites (underlined), respectively.

Mud loach *mlc2f* promoter was integrated to the cfp structural gene from the commercial CFP vector (Clontech). The resultant 7 kb reporter vector was labelled as pmmmlc2CFP and the sequence of expression cassette (i.e. from the 5'-end of *mlc2f* promoter to the 3'-end of the cfp structural gene) was confirmed.

2.5. Microinjection and fluorescence expression analysis

2.5.1. Plasmid preparation

The pmmmlc2CFP plasmid was amplified using XL1-blue MRF' *Escherichia coli* strain (Stratagene, LA Jolla, CA, USA), purified using alkaline lysis method and resuspended in an injection buffer (10mM Tris-Cl, 0.1 mM EDTA, pH 8.0) at a final concentration of 100 µg/ml.

2.5.2. Broodstock management

Mud loach and albino loach were maintained in Laboratory of Fish Genetic Resources & Engineering Laboratory, Pukyong National University, Busan, Korea. Water temperature was kept at 25-26°C. Broodstock was fed at 10% of body weight with moisture pellet (80%) and commercial diet (20%) (Ewha Feed Co. Ltd., Korea).

2.5.3. Spawning induction

Mature male and female mud loach were induced to spawning with an injection of carp pituitary extract (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, Missouri, USA) at 10 µg per g body weight. Weight of female mud loach range from 15-23 g while the weight of male ranged from 22-28 g. Female mud loach began to spawn at about 13 hours post hormone injection. Female with the best quality of eggs (examined by color, shape and size uniformity) was then selected for artificial fertilization. For minimizing the stress during egg and sperm stripping, male and female loach were anaesthetize in 300 ppm of lidocaine (Daeshin Pharm and Trading Co. Ltd.) supplemented with 3 ppt of sodium bicarbonate (Duksan Pure Chemicals, Kyungkido, Korea).

Sperm was stripped and kept in 1.5 ml micro centrifuge tube and diluted 1 : 10 with ice-cold saline solution and stored on ice until fertilization. Eggs were stripped into glass petri dish (φ12 mm) and fertilization was performed with the diluted sperm. After adding and washing with water, fertilized eggs (150 - 200) were transferred to glass petri dish (φ9 mm). After the eggs attaching to the dish, carefully the dishes were washed and a small number of eggs were incubated at 25°C. The remaining eggs were transferred to water bath.

2.5.4. Microinjection

After fertilization, eggs were kept in water bath at 16, 19 or 23°C for halting the embryonic development. At one celled-embryo, DNA was microinjected into the center of blastomere using microcapillary needle (Idaho technology) attached to a micromanipulator. Uninjected or dead eggs were

removed while the number of injected eggs were recorded. Microcapillary needles were prepared using Narishige PC-10 Puller (Narishige Scientific Instrument Lab, Tokyo, Japan). The tip of pulled needle was punctured to make an opening hole with a size 3-4 μm . The maximum volume of DNA injected to blastomere was about 10 nl. Microinjection was conducted using a Narishige MMN-330 micromanipulator (Narishige Scientific Instrument Lab). Microinjection was carried out under stereo zoom microscope Motic, SMZ161 (Motic Asia, Hongkong). After microinjection, embryos were transferred to a 25°C incubation tank until hatching.

2.5.5. Identification of CFP positive embryos

During embryonic development, microinjected embryos were examined with Epi-fluorescent microscope. Cyan fluorescent protein was observed with an AZ100 Multi Purpose Zoom Epi-fluorescent microscope supported by the NIS-Elements BR image analysis software (Nikon Corporation Instruments Inc, Japan.) according to manufacturer's instruction.

CFP expression was examined with the Nikon CFP filter (excitation filter wavelengths: 426-446 nm; dichromic mirror cut-on wavelength: 455 nm; and barrier filter wavelengths: 460-500 nm). Expression of CFP was photographed using the digital camera (Nikon Digital Sight DS-R11) mounted in the epi-fluorescent microscope.

After yolk sac absorption was completed, at 36 hours, larvae were fed with commercial powdered diet (Ewha Feed Co). At 1 week of age, larvae were supplemented with minced sludge worm and were supplied with pump and filtration system.

2.6. Germline transmission test and phenotype analysis

Presumed transgenic male loach was selected for germline transmission due to their capability to produce sperm frequently and at any time. At adult stage, ten male transgenic founders were selected based on strength and areas of CFP signals in their body. Selection was carried out using portable blue light flash.

Selected transgenic founders were subjected to PCR analysis of their caudal fin and sperm to confirm the existence of transgene. PCR and sperm-positive founders were mated with non-transgenic wild type to examine the germline transmission to the subsequent generation. Spawning induction and mating were conducted with similar method as for microinjection.

F1 embryos were examined per mating group at somite formation stage, prehatching stage and after hatching stage. CFP positive larvae were transferred to a 25°C hatching tank. Water exchange was conducted twice per day at 80% of total rearing water. Every two days, the surface of rearing tank was cleaned using rubber scraper.

Exogenous feeding was started at two days post hatching. Uneaten diet were siphoned out daily from rearing tank. As starter feed, yeast powder was mixed with water and then spread evenly to water column. Feeding with commercial diet was started at 4 dph. Pump and filtration system were assembled at the center of rearing tank at 1 week post hatching, Larvae were further cultured until maturation and mated with wild type albino loach to produce F2 generation.

2.7. Histology analysis of muscle from fluorescent transgenic fish

The procedure of fixing and paraffin embedding muscle of fluorescent transgenic fish are as follows:

- 1) collect the tissue from the specimen
- 2) place tissue in cassette with biopsy pad
- 3) let sit in pre-cooled 95% ethanol for 15-24 hours at 4°C, depending of the harvest time
- 4) move the samples through four changes of pre cooled 100% ethanol for 1-2 hours each, at 4°C
- 5) clear in three changes of pre-cooled xylenes for 1-2 hours each at 4°C
- 6) run specimen through four baths of 56°C paraffin for 10-12 hours each
- 7) store embedded specimen block at 4°C and away from light
- 8) cut section of block 10 µm thick
- 9) float sections at 50°C water baths for as short as duration as possible
- 10) bake slides at 33°C for 30 minutes
- 11) wash slides in three changes of cold xylene for 2 minute each, with gentle agitation
- 12) remove xylene with three changes of cold 95% ethanol for 2 minute each, with gentle agitation.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Characteristics of mud loach *mlc2f* cDNA and deduced amino acid

Mud loach (*Misgurnus mizolepis*) *mlc2f* cDNA comprises 61 bp 5'-UTR, 510 bp open reading frame encoding a 169-aa polypeptide and 293 bp 3'-UTR excluding a 19 bp polyA tail. Polyadenylation signal (AATAAA) occurs at 29 bp before polyA tail (Fig. 1).

The Genomic organization of the primary structure of deduced polypeptide of the mud loach myosin light chain 2 was compared with those of previously known vertebrate orthologues compiled from the public databases including the GenBank (Fig. 2).

Deduced polypeptide sequence of mud loach MLC2f share structural homology with other teleostean, amphibian and mammalian. Theoretical pI and molecular weight (MW) of mud loach MLC2f are calculated to be 4.69 and 18.8 kDa, respectively using the Expasy ProtParam tool (www.expasy.org/protparam).

Database search using BLAST software for protein show that mud loach MLC2f conserve the helix-loop-helix structure which is common found in MLC2 vertebrate. The N terminus of MLC2f polypeptide showed less conserved region as compared with central region and C terminus.

The MLC2f embody EFh superfamily domain which cover residues between 25 to 88 amino acid. Amino acid alignment resulted in 99% identity with channel catfish (*Ictalurus punctatus*), common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) and Korean oily bitterling (*Acheilognathus koreensis*).

3.2. Genomic DNA organization and phylogeny tree of mud loach *mlc2f* gene

Genomic mud loach *mlc2f* represented 7 exons (64, 96, 76, 105, 79, 49 and 99 bp, respectively for coding regions) interfered by six introns (704, 1464, 87, 89, 95 and 89 bp, respectively). Mud loach *mlc2f* seven exons interrupted by six introns share similar structure with Korean oily bitterling. Other than exon 1 and exon 7, both species share similar length of remaining 5 exons. Teleost *mlc2f* consists of two paralogues: *mlc2fa* and *mlc2fb*. The *mlc2fa* consist of 7 exons interrupted by 6 introns while teleost *mlc2fb* consist of 6 exons (Lee *et al.*, 2013) (Fig. 3). Phylogeny tree showed that mud loach *mlc2f* is placed among teleost *mlc2fa* clade and clustered with channel catfish and common carp. According to the phylogeny tree, *mlc2fa* is an ortholog to tetrapod, while another isoform, *mlc2fb* was paralog to teleost *mlc2fa* (Fig. 4).

3.3. Structural characteristics of mud loach *mlc2f* promoter and construction of expression vector

The most common transcription factor is E-box transcription factor. Three copies of myocyte enhancer factor-2 (MEF2) were distributed throughout the 5'-flanking region.

Fig. 3. Schematic representation to show the genomic organization of mud loach (*Misgurnus mizolepis*) *mlc2f* gene .

Fig. 4. Reconstructed N-J phylogeny tree for teleost and tetrapod *mlc2f*, including mud loach *mlc2f* gene

MEF2 family of transcription factors play an important function during embryonic development. Specific pattern of MEF2 genes during embryogenesis reveal the function or role during regulation of muscle-specific transcript during development of cardiac and skeletal muscle.

Other than the two transcription factors, several other transcription factors were also predicted, such as : CAAT, STAT, GATA, MZF-1, Cdx, Nkx-2.5, AP-1, TFIID and CArg. Twelve E-box copies were predicted.

E-box is a protein binding site that function to regulate gene expression in muscles and other tissues. MyoD protein that bind to E-box has a role in construction and formation of muscular tissues (Fig. 5)

A circular pmmmlc2fCFP construct was used for microinjection experiment to generate transgenic mud loach carrying cyan fluorescent protein (Fig. 6).

3.4. Survival and CFP expression pattern in microinjected embryos and hatched larvae of mud loach and albino loach

Microinjection was conducted to 1330 fertilized eggs of mud loach (Table 1) using the pmmmlc2CFP vector. The percentage of survival eggs at 30 myotomes stage (21 hpf) was 41.5% and percentage of hatched larvae was 18.6%.

A total of 248 larvae hatched (18.6%) after injection trial. Roughly 33.8% of hatched larvae or 6.3% out of injected embryos exhibited CFP expression under fluorescent microscope.

Fig. 5. Predicted transcription factor binding motifs in the 5' flanking region of mud loach *mlc2f* gene.

Fig. 6. Partial restriction map of pmmmlc2CFP vector used for microinjection.

Table 1. Survival and hatching rate of mud loach embryos injected with pmmmlc2CFP

Transgenic line	Injected egg	Survival rate (%)	Hatching rate (%)	CFP positive embryos (%)
Mud loach	1330	41.5	18.6	33.8

Microinjection was conducted to 1996 fertilized eggs of albino loach (Table 2). The percentage of survival egg at 30 myotomes stage was 53.2% and percentage of hatched larva was 12.4%. A total of 248 larvae hatched after injection trial. Roughly 28.6% of hatched larvae or 3.5% out of injected embryos exhibited CFP expression under fluorescent microscope.

Initial CFP expression in mud loach was observed at 20-21 myotome stage, disappearance of Kupffer's vesicle, 19 hpf (Kim *et al.*, 1987). The CFP signal was initially observed weakly at the anterior somite (Fig. 7), but the signal intensity become stronger and distributed in more surface area of skeletal muscle during the latter stage of embryonic development, especially before hatching. Upon hatching, the larva display strong CFP signal only in skeletal muscle. Strength of CFP signal was scattered randomly along the body myomere. During early larva, CFP signal greatly intensified. All CFP-positive founders showed variable strength of CFP signals in their body, indicating mosaicism that is normally occurred in injected embryos (Ju *et al.*, 1999; 2003; Cho *et al.*, 2011; 2013). During embryonic and early larva hatching stage, CFP signals were exclusively expressed in skeletal muscle.

The *pmmmlc2CFP* vector successfully driven the expression of CFP during embryo and larva stage of albino loach. Mosaic expression of CFP signal was observed during the embryonic stage but the signal intensity become stronger and distributed in more surface area of skeletal muscle during the latter stage of embryonic development, especially before hatching (Fig. 8). Upon hatching, the larva display strong CFP signal only in skeletal muscle. Ectopic expression such as expression in egg yolk and intestine was not observed indicating a strict expression *mlc2f* vector in skeletal muscle.

Table 2. Survival and hatching rate of albino loach embryos injected with pmmmlc2CFP

Transgenic line	Injected egg	Survival rate (%)	Hatching rate (%)	CFP positive embryos (%)
Albino loach	1996	53.2	12.4	28.6

Fig. 7. Muscle expression of CFP signals in embryo and larva of mud loach microinjected with pmmmlc2CFP vector. Image D and D' was taken as lateral view of newly hatched larvae at 0 dph. Exposure time for each figure was 200 ms. Scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Fig. 8. CFP expression in embryonic and larval muscles of albino loach developed from eggs microinjected with pmmmlc2CFP vector. Image C and C' was taken as ventrolateral view of newly hatched larvae at 0 dph. Exposure time for each figure was 200 ms. Scale bar = 0.5 mm.

CFP signals was scattered randomly along the body myomere. During early larva development, CFP signal greatly intensified. All CFP-positive founders showed variable strength of CFP signals in their body, indicating mosaicism that is normally occurred in any injected embryos (Ju *et al.*, 1999; 2003; Cho *et al.*, 2011; 2013). At juvenile stage (20 dph) CFP signals could be observed in lower jaw (Fig. 9). CFP signals was not distributed evenly.

3.5. CFP expression pattern in mature founder generation

CFP-positive larvae were maintained and raised until sexual maturation. After 11 months of rearing, 66 fish (75.0%) survive and reach sexual maturity from 88 CFP-positive larvae. Ratio of female to male was 35 : 31. Based on the intensity and expression area, all CFP founders exhibit mosaic expression of CFP signals in their body (Fig. 9). Upon reaching maturation, CFP signal was observed as patches of CFP pattern in the skeletal body. However, CFP signal was only visible with the aid of blue light

3.6. Germline transmission test in transgenic founder of mud loach and albino loach and resultant CFP expression in F1 generation

Two of transgenic adult mud loach male with PCR and sperm-positive result are selected for germline transmission (Fig. 10). Weight of each transgenic founder was 9.54 gr and 11.43 gr. Candidate of transgenic founders were mated with mature albino female. Spawning was conducted and the number of fertilized egg, survived embryo and hatched larva was recorded.

Fig. 9. Mosaic expression pattern of CFP signals in juvenile mud loach founder developed from eggs microinjected with pmm1c2CFP vector. All panels in the right sides are higher magnification of CFP expression areas of the left side panel. Dark field pictures were taken with 200 ms of exposure time.

Fig. 10. External CFP-phenotype of transgenic founders that were subjected to germ-line transmission test. Picture was taken under normal light (A, B) and blue light (A', B').

Table 3. Germline transmission test in transgenic mud loach of F0 generation

Transgenic line	Generation	Survival rate (%)	Hatching rate (%)	CFP-positive embryos (%)
Mud loach	F0 to F1	67.5	67.2	4.0

Table 4. Germline transmission test in transgenic albino loach of F0 generation

Transgenic line	Generation	Survival rate (%)	Hatching rate (%)	CFP-positive embryos (%)
Albino loach	F0 to F1	83.7	78.7	2.7

The CFP-positive larva hatching percentage was 4.0% while total hatching rate was 67.2%. From the total of 23 mature albino loach expressing CFP signals with chimeric pattern, one of mature male (9 months post hatching) was selected for germline transmission. CFP signals covered between 20-30% of the whole body. Male albino loach was then mated with a wild type albino female to obtain the F1 generation of albino loach carrying cyan fluorescent protein.

In this experiment, we established a generation of transgenic albino loach carrying a fluorescent reporter. Among the fry that was produced, 12 larvae from the total of 440 hatched larvae were observed with CFP signal in their skeletal muscle (Table 3). Percentage of hatched larvae that express CFP signal was 2.7% while hatching rate was 78.7%. Transmission rate from founder generation to F1 generation of both mud loach (4.0%) and albino loach (2.7%) was lower than that was found in zebrafish (10%) carrying GFP or marine medaka carrying RFP protein, both driven by *mlc2* promoter (Ju *et al.*, 2003; Cho *et al.*, 2013) (Table 4).

Expression of CFP signals in skeletal muscle under the control of *mlc2f* promoter was clearly observed in F1 hemizygote as compared to mosaic founders (Fig. 11). CFP signals were first observed at 12 hours post hatching (hph) in skeletal muscle which is much later as compared to microinjected founder. During early larvae development, the intensity of CFP signals increased uniformly along the lateral muscle. At 62 hph, weak CFP signals were observed in levator arcus palatini and pectoral fin-attaching muscles. The CFP signals were intensified at 131 hph (5 dph) and 199 hph (8 dph). From 131 hph, the lateral muscle (myotomes) started to increase in thickness.

Fig. 11. Expression of CFP in F1 transgenic mud loach larva. Light and dark-field photographs were taken to show CFP expression. Expression pattern was observed and photographed from 12 hph to 199 hph. From 12 hph until 36 hph, photographs were taken as lateral view, while from 62 hph to 199 hph, photographs were taken as dorsal view. In the photographs, eye, pectoral fin-attaching muscle (pfm), epaxial muscle (epm), levator arcus palatini (lap) are indicated by arrows. Exposure time for each figure was 200 ms.

Fig. 12. Expression of CFP in F1 transgenic mud loach larva at 8 and 16 dph. Light and dark-field images were taken to show CFP expression. Exposure time for each dark-field image was 200 ms

In a small teleost fish, *Poecilia reticulata*, epaxial muscle area increase 24% from 3 dph to 10 dph, and increase 223% from 20 dph to 27 dph (Veggetti *et al.*, 1993). In sea bream (*Dicentrarchus labrax*), myotomes almost doubled from hatching to 10 dph (Veggetti *et al.*, 1990). During early larva life, the presumptive fast muscle increases in mass by addition of new fibres from presumptive myoblast beneath the slow muscle layer (Veggetti *et al.*, 1990)

At 8 dph, CFP signal was strongly expressed in head muscle and pectoral fin muscle (Fig. 12). In head muscle, the strongest expression was found in a pair of levator arcus palatine muscle. Levator arcus palatine attached to fish mandibulae (lower jaw) and involved in feeding activity (Diogo *et al.*, 2008). At 8 dph the size of the head was wider than the wide of body. After 16 dph, body muscles started to bulked up until almost the size of head. Signal of CFP was disappeared from the pectoral fin adductor muscle at 16 dph. This was probably due to the development of pectoral fin rays. The pectoral fin rays of cyprinid loach started to develop at 13-14 dph and completed between 23-30 dph (Gao *et al.*, 2014).

In transgenic albino loach aged 2 dph, CFP signal was weakly expressed in pectoral fin attaching muscle and head muscle while at 5 dph, the CFP signal was strongly expressed in pectoral fin attaching muscle and head muscle (levator arcus palatine). The pectoral fin bud and external gill filament could be observed at 2 dph. Newly hatched larva (0-2 dph) were usually remain motionless at the tank surface. If disturbed, larva will propel themselves, suddenly stop and drop down to the tank. At 5 dph, larva increase its activity and swim occasionally (Fig. 13).

Fig. 13. Expression of CFP in F1 transgenic albino loach larva at 2 and 5 dph. Photographs were taken as dorsal view of whole body. Fin-attaching muscle (pfm), caudal fin muscle (cfm), levator arcus palatine (lap), adductor mandibulae (am), intermandibularis anterior (ima), intermandibularis posterior (imp), interhyoideus (ih), hyohyoideus (hh), sternohyoideus (sh) were indicated by arrows. Scale bar = 1 mm.

At 2 dph and 5 dph, the dorsal head muscle was not expressed. Other than pectoral fin attaching muscle, cfp signal was not discovered in dorsal, anal, pelvic fin attaching muscle. At 2 dph majority of CFP signal was found at the anterior part of skeletal muscle, while at 5 dph, CFP signals was also expressed weakly at the posterior of body. At 5 dph the external gill filament and pectoral fin bud was reduced and the gill operculum was completely covered gill filament. Stomach extension indicate active feed consumption.

At 8 dph, CFP signal was expressed intensely at head muscle (levator arcus palatine), pectoral fin attaching muscle, and skeletal muscle. The anlagen of dorsal and anal fin were clearly observed without expression of CFP in each of fin muscle. In case of transgenic mud loach carrying CFP, the signal was visible in dorsal and anal fin muscle. It is possible that albino loach has a slightly later of CFP expression in fin muscles. CFP expression in caudal fin muscle could be observed close to hypural bone (Fig. 14). Several fin rays could be visible in pectoral fin (A) and caudal fin (D). Three pairs of barbels had developed at ventral tip of mouth. Median fin membrane was not completely disappeared at 8 dph.

At 20 dph (post flexion larva), CFP signal was thickly expressed in the skeletal muscle (Fig. 15). Pectoral fin muscle and caudal fin muscle express strong CFP signal. Caudal fin rays almost developed completely, however the median fin was remain at dorsal and ventral of caudal peduncle but completely discernible from caudal fin. Median fin membrane was completely disappeared at 20 dph. The dark area in B' indicate gill compartment. CFP signal was expressed uniformly at whole body of skeletal muscle except for the ventral region. Sarcomere pattern could easily be seen in skeletal muscle.

Fig. 14. Expression of CFP in F1 transgenic albino loach larva at 8 dph. Expression pattern was observed and photographs were taken as dorsal view (A and A') and lateral view (B, B', C, C', D, D'). Pectoral fin-attaching muscle (pfm) and caudal fin muscle (cfm) were indicated by bracket (A'). Anlagen of dorsal fin (adf), anlagen of anal fin (aaf), epaxial muscle (epm), hypaxial muscle (hpm), horizontal myoseptum (hm), adductor mandibulae (am), flexor dorsalis (fd), flexor ventralis (fv), hypochordal longitudinalis (hl) are indicated by arrows. Scale bar = 1 mm.

Fig. 15. Expression of CFP in F1 transgenic albino loach at 20 dph. Light and dark-field photographs were taken to show CFP expression. Photographs were taken as lateral view of whole body (A, A') or parts of whole body (B, B', C, C', D, D'). Hypural bones (hb) and caudal fin muscle (cfm) were indicated by bracket while fin ray (fr) was indicated by arrow (D, D'). Epaxial muscle (epm), hypaxial muscle (hpm), horizontal myoseptum (hmy), adductor mandibulae (am) are indicated by arrows (B'). Exposure time for each dark-field figure was 200 ms. Scale bar = 1 mm.

3.7. CFP signals in various organs or tissues removed from F1 adults of transgenic mud loach

Strong expression of CFP signals could be observed in muscle tissue. Ectopic expression of *mlc2f*CFP in smooth (intestine, kidney, liver, spleen) and cardiac (heart) muscle was not found, indicating strict expression of *mlc2f* promoter in skeletal muscle of mud loach (Fig. 16).

3.8. Expression of *mlc2f* and CFP mRNA in adult tissues

Based on qRT-PCR results, *mlc2f* and CFP mRNAs were mainly found in skeletal muscle tissue (Fig. 17). Moderate level of *mlc2f* expression were found from gill and skin. Similar with the endogenous *mlc2f* expression, the expression pattern of transgenic CFP mRNA driven by the *mlc2f* promoter was also highly muscle-predominant (Fig. 17). Strong expression in skeletal muscle and weaker expression in gill could also be found in other fishes such as marine medaka (Cho *et al.*, 2013; Lee *et al.*, 2013) and Korean oily bitterling (Kong *et al.*, 2013). Dominant skeletal muscle expression has been reported in gilthead sea bream (Moutou *et al.*, 2001) and zebrafish (Ju *et al.*, 2003).

3.9. External CFP phenotype from F1 adults of transgenic mud loach

Expression of CFP signals was reliably expressed in skeletal muscle of the whole body throughout the life cycle of F1 generation. CFP signals were absent in the cranial region but appear at the lower jaw muscles. F1 transgenic fish display mild greenish body color (Fig. 18).

Fig. 16. CFP signals in various organs or tissues removed from F1 transgenic adults. Light and dark-field photographs were taken to show CFP expression. Exposure time for each dark-field figure was 200 ms

Fig. 17. Distribution pattern and expression of endogenous *mlc2f* and CFP mRNAs in adult tissues. Tissue abbreviations are brain (BR), eye (EY), fin (FI), gill (GI), intestine (IN), kidney (KI), liver (LI), muscle (MU) and skin (SK).

Fig. 18. External view of F1 CFP-transgenics and their non-transgenic sibling. Picture was taken using ordinary fluorescent light (A) and blue LED light (A').

However, if the F1 transgenic fish was shed with blue LED light, a bright green glow could be observed from their body. Body size and weight of F1 transgenic fish are comparable with F1 non-transgenic fish meaning there was not any negative effect of transgene to fish growth.

Female transgenic of F1 generation have larger body as compared to the male. There is no abnormal swimming pattern which mean that the *mlc2f* promoter has no negative effect to swimming capability. The pigmented patch that cover body block the expression of CFP signals.

The CFP signal was not observable along the body lateral line and dorsal line. CFP signal also absent in each fin rays and fin attaching muscle, including caudal fin muscle. This pattern is not similar as transgenic marine medaka carrying cyan fluorescent protein driven by *mlc2f* promoter. Caudal fin attaching muscle of marine medaka express strong CFP sign that is visible with unaided eye (Cho *et al.*, 2013; Vu *et al.*, 2014).

3.10. Germline transmission test in transgenic F1 generation of albino loach and hybrid loach (mud loach X albino loach) and resultant CFP expression in F2 generation

Two of transgenic albino loach male of F1 generation were selected and mated with wild type albino female to produce F2 generation. Weight of each adult F1 generation was 3.36 g and 3.23 g. Result of germline transmission test was shown in Table 6. The CFP transgene was successfully transmitted to F2 generation.

Table 5. Germline transmission test in transgenic albino loach of F1 generation

Transgenic line	Generation	Survival rate (%)	Hatching rate (%)	CFP-positive embryos (%)
Albino loach	F1 to F2	20.0	11.4	42.9

Normally, the percentage of CFP positive embryos in F2 generation should follow the Mendelian ratio (50%). Unfortunately, the incidence of CFP positive larva was less than 50% (42.9%). The cause of this pattern could be down to the low survival and hatching rate percentage.

Initial hatching was recorded at 36 hours post fertilization and mass hatching was occurred two to three hours after initial hatching. Hatching occurred at 12 hours later if compared to mud loach (*Misgurnus mizolepis*) larva (Kim *et al.*, 1987).

Within an hour after hatching, the larva display weak CFP signals in anterior part of skeletal muscle close to the head (Fig 19). As the larva development progressed, F2 larvae showed an intensified CFP signals that spread toward the caudal peduncle.

The region with strongest CFP signals was located at 1/3 anterior of the whole body (Fig 19). However, the external gill filament will be retracted at 3, 4 dph and completely disappeared at 5 dph (Gao *et al.*, 2014). Pectoral fin bud started to develop at 2 dph and expand almost the size of the head at 3 dph (Fig. 20).

CFP signal started appeared weakly at levator arcus palatine muscle (lap) and pectoral fin attaching muscle (pfm) at 3 dph. This pattern is slightly later as compared with transgenic mud loach which expressed strong CFP signals at levator arcus palatine and pectoral muscle.

Hypaxial, epaxial and horizontal myoseptum were not distinguishable. Each myomeres of skeletal muscle expressed CFP signal uniformly unlike CFP signals of microinjected larva.

Fig. 19. Expression of CFP in F2 transgenic albino loach at 0 and 2 hph. Light and dark-field photographs were taken to show CFP expression. Photographs were taken as dorsal view of whole body. Exposure time for each dark-field figure was 1000 ms. External gill filament was not observed at 0 dph but observable at 2 dph.

Fig. 20. Expression of CFP in F2 transgenic albino loach larva at 0-3 dph. Light and dark-field photographs were taken to show CFP expression. Photograph was taken as lateral view of whole body except in D, D' which is dorsal view of whole body. Exposure time for each dark field figure was 1000 ms. Scale bar = 0.5 mm.

Fig. 21. Expression of CFP in F2 transgenic albino loach larva at 4 dph. Light and dark-field photographs were taken to show CFP expression. Image A and A' was taken as lateral view of whole body while Image B and B' was taken as dorsal view of body. Levator arcus palatine (lap), adductor mandibulae (am), intermandibularis posterior (imp), interhyoideus (ih), hyohyoideus (hh), sternohyoideus (sh), epaxial muscle (epm), hypaxial muscle (hpm), horizontal myoseptum (hmy), adductor mandibulae (am) are indicated by arrows were indicated by arrows. Exposure time for each dark field figure was 1000 ms. Scale bar = 1 mm.

Fig. 22. Expression of CFP in F2 transgenic albino loach larva at 20 dph. Image A and A' was taken as ventrolateral view of whole body while Image B and B' was taken as ventrolateral view of head. Image C and C' was taken as ventral view of head Adductor mandibulae (am), intermandibularis anterior (ima), intermandibularis posterior (imp), interhyoideus (ih), hyohyoideus (hh), sternohyoideus (sh), are indicated by arrows were indicated by arrows. Exposure time for each dark field figure was 1000 ms. Scale bar = 1 mm. Identification of cranial muscles are based on Schilling *et al.* (1997)

At 3 dph, transgenic larva carrying CFP signal in their skeletal muscle could be distinguished from non-transgenic larva without the aid of blue light. Using a black colored rearing tank, the CFP signals in skeletal muscle appeared green yellow without the aid of blue LED light under common fluorescent light bulb. Similar pattern of green yellow could also be found from transgenic marine medaka bearing cyan fluorescent protein driven by *mlc2f* promoter (Vu *et al.*, 2014).

During the first two days after hatching, loach larva was usually found laying using their body side, while at 3 dph, larva was found upward with their ventral body attached to the tank surface.

At 4 dph (preflexion larva), lateral head muscle and dorsal head muscle expressed strong CFP signals. Area between epaxial and hypaxial muscle (horizontal myoseptum) could be discernible (Fig. 21). Size of external gill was reduced and pectoral fin was slightly crooked and angled. Expression of CFP signals at pectoral fin was intensified. Barbel under the mouth started to branch. There is still no expression of CFP signal at anlagen of dorsal, caudal pelvic and anal fin.

Expression of mud loach hyoid muscle at 20 dph was stronger than at 4 dph (Fig. 22), especially adductor mandibulae and hyohyoideus muscles. Adductor mandibulae main function was related with adduction of mandibulae (primary jaw closing muscles). Other than for feeding, pharyngeal muscle (hyoid muscles) and jaw muscle (adductor mandibulae) also responsible during direct respiration. When a fish gulping air from the water surface, adductor arcus palatini, geniohyoideus and adductor mandibulae compress the buccal cavity and removing as much as possible water inside buccal cavity chamber.

Table 6. Germline transmission test in transgenic hybrid loach (mud loach x albino loach) of F1 generation.

Transgenic line	Generation	Survival rate (%)	Hatching rate (%)	CFP-positive embryos (%)
Hybrid (Mud loach x Albino loach)	F1 to F2	48.0	32.6	48.7

Table 7. Segregation of pigmented and albino phenotype in transgenic mud loach of F2 generation

Mating groups (Backcross)	Pigmented larva		Albino larva	
	CFP positive	CFP Negative	CFP positive	CFP Negative
TG hybrid (mud loach x alb. loach)	70	54	59	82
X Non TG alb.loach				

Fig. 23. Expression of CFP in F2 transgenic pigmented and albino loach larva at 8 dph. Light and dark-field photographs were taken to show CFP expression. Expression pattern was observed and photographs were taken as lateral view. Pectoral fin-attaching muscle (pfm), dorsal fin muscle (dfm), anal fin muscle (afm) and caudal fin muscle (cfm) were indicated by bracket (A'). Epaxial muscle (epm), hypaxial muscle (hpm), horizontal myoseptum (hmy), adductor mandibulae (am) are indicated by arrows (B'). Exposure time for dark-field figure was 200 ms. Scale bar = 1 mm.

Upon reaching the water surface, levator arcus palatini and sternohyoideus muscle expand volume the buccal cavity. Sudden expansion of buccal cavity create air suction from the water surface into the buccal cavity. Again, after the mouth was closed, adductor arcus palatini, geniohyoideus and adductor mandibulae compressed air inside the buccal cavity, forcing old air out and new air into chamber (Liem, 1980).

After 7 months of rearing, several F1 generation of transgenic mud loach reach sexual maturity. Three transgenic adult male were selected and mated with wild type albino female to produce F2 generation. Weight of each transgenic male was 7.20, 5.12, and 5.14 g. Result of germline transmission test was shown in Table 6. The CFP transgene was successfully transmitted to F2 generation. Result of germline transmission test (48.7%) show that transmission of CFP transgene to F2 generation follow the Mendelian ratio.

Female albino parents contribute to the genetic information to the F1 generation. However, due to the state of albino as a recessive gene, the albino phenotype was not expressed. Transgenic mud loach of F1 generation are carrier of albino gene. Transgenic F1 generation was mated with wild type albino which yield 53.2% albino and 46.8% pigmented larva or 48.6% transgenic and 51.3% non-transgenic progeny (Table 7).

At 8 dph (flexion larva stage), fin rays of dorsal, caudal and anal fin were started to develop. Fin membrane covers entire dorsal area, caudal area until base of anus. Melanophores covered the entire body surface including fin membrane. Parts of cranial muscle could be distinguished only in albino loach larvae but not possible in pigmented mud loach larva (Fig. 23).

3.11. Muscle histology in F1/F2 generation

Ventral part of mud loach head muscle were dominated by hyoid muscles (Fig. 24). Horizontal septum separate hypaxialis muscle and epaxialis muscle, while vertical septum separate left and right muscle (Fig. 25). Axial fish muscle is arranged into section of myotomes. Lateral view of myotome showed stacked cone arrangement (Fig. 26). During contraction, the height of myotome cone was shorten while the cone radius was increased. (Westneat *et al.*, 1993) After contraction the myotome cone return to its resting state (longer cone height and shorter radius). The axial muscle of fish can be classified into two types, fast twitch or white muscle and slow twitch or red muscle. The fish that swim constantly have more slow muscle than benthic species. The slow muscle in most fish is located under the lateral line. The shape of slow muscle is usually triangular in cross section (Videler, 1993).

In eel-like swimmer (as in loach), slow muscle was distributed along the body. Power and thrust are created by prolonged undulatory movement along the body. At any given time, muscle is active on both side of body. In case of tuna, thrust was produced by short, discrete bursts of thrust at the tail (Altringham and Shadwick, 2001).

In juvenile loach, muscle fibres of different size could be seen inside axial muscle (Fig. 25) After the early (embryonic and larva) stage, juvenile experience mosaic hyperplasia growth in which fish reach large final size. At this stage, mosaic appearance of muscle fibre was common and fibres of different sizes intermingled in fast-white muscle (Veggetti *et al.*, 1990; Silva *et al.*, 2008).

Main and secondary horizontal myoseptum (hmy) are fibrous connective tissue sheet separating the myotome into dorsal and ventral part (Fig. 25). Main horizontal myoseptum is visible as dark line running through the middle of myotome (Fig. 26).

Main horizontal myoseptum is present in all jawed fish and terrestrial vertebrate but are not exist in jawless fish (Bone, 1989; Eeden *et al.*, 1996; Currie and Ingham, 2001). It is one of three features that are recognizable in myotome during the course of embryonic development. The other two features are adaxial cells and muscle pioneer. Absence or reduced growth of horizontal myoseptum affected the development of muscle pioneer during embryonic development of zebrafish (Eeden *et al.*, 1996).

Infracarinalis and supracarinalis muscle are pairs of narrow muscles located along the ventral and dorsal margin of caudal peduncle (Fig. 26). Role of each muscle are for abduction of dorsal and ventral lobe of fin and lateral flexion of the fin. In an experiment with bluegill sunfish (*Lepomis macrochirus*), Supracarinalis (sc) muscle and infracarinalis (ic) muscle are occasionally active during low speed swimming (0.5 Ls^{-1}). Increasing swimming speed ($1.2 - 2 \text{ Ls}^{-1}$) resulted in upsurge of 50-100% of muscle burst intensity and sudden activity of other caudal fin muscles (Flammang and Lauder, 2008).

The posterior part of infracarinalis and supracarinalis muscle hold and support the beginning of caudal fin ray, both the ventral and dorsal most of fin lobes. Contraction of both muscles flare caudal fin lobes (Westneat and Wainwright, 2001)

Fig. 24. Sagittal sections of cranial muscle of 12-week-old F2 albino loach. Epaxial muscle (epm), hyoid muscle (hm) are indicated by arrows. Scale bar = 1 mm.

Fig. 25. Transverse sections of lateral muscle of 12-week-old F2 albino loach. Infracarinalis muscle (im); supracarinalis muscle (sm); horizontal myoseptum (hmy); vertical septum (vs); skin (sk); white muscle (w); vertebrate (v) are indicated by arrows. Scale bar = 1 mm.

Fig. 26. Sagittal sections of caudal peduncle muscle of 12-week-old F2 albino loach. Infracarinalis muscle (im); supracarinalis muscle (sm); horizontal myoseptum (hmy); flexor dorsalis (fd); flexor ventralis (fv); interradialis (ir) are indicated by arrows. Scale bar = 1 mm.

Interradialis (ir) muscles located at the base of caudal fin rays. This muscle role during swimming was to adduct each fin rays after contraction of hypochordal longitudinalis (hl) muscle. Each interradialis muscle of one caudal fin ray contract independently without any affect to another interradialis muscle. Adduction of caudal fin rays by ir and hl muscle resulted in reduction of the caudal fin surface area while abduction of caudal fin by flexor dorsalis (fd), flexor ventralis (fv), supracarinalis (sc) and infracarinalis (ic) muscles resulted in an increase of caudal fin surface area (Flammang and Lauder, 2008).

Pattern of CFP expression was transmitted successfully and was retained constantly during the F1 and F2 generation regardless of the species (mud loach or albino loach). Ectopic expression was not observed at any generation and between species. This result means that *mhc2f* promoter strictly drive the expression of fluorescent protein in fish skeletal muscle.

Mud loach *mhc2f* conserved the EFhand domain which is typical of vertebrate *mhc2*. Also the genomic structure of 7 exons interrupted by 6 introns which is conserved in vertebrate orthologues. Based on the phylogeny tree and amino acid alignment, mud loach share 99% identity with common carp, channel catfish and Korean oily bitterling.

Expression of MLC2 in mud loach and albino loach occurred after hatching. This pattern was also found in other fish. CFP signal could be observed in late somite stage of microinjected embryo in both of the loach species. However, the albino loach has longer incubation time (36 hours) as compared to mud loach (24 hours). Similar period and temperature of larva incubation was also observed in cyprinid loach (*Misgurnus anguillicaudatus*).

It appeared that during the early period, larva movement was primarily propelled by pectoral fin rather than caudal fins. Moreover, large size of pectoral fin started developed from 2 dph or at the initiation of exogenous feeding. Survival of larva was decided by the capability to swim during transition to exogenous feeding (Morioka *et al.*, 2009).

Pectoral fin muscle and head muscle of mud loach was expressed much earlier (5 dph) than caudal and anal fin (8 dph). According to Gao (2014), caudal length has negative allometric growth compared with other body parts during the early larva stage.

If we compare albino loach and mud loach, there is one difference of expression pattern. At 8 dph, mud loach showed CFP signals at all fin muscle, while in albino loach, CFP signals was observed only in pectoral and caudal fin, but not in dorsal and anal fin.

CFP expression was visible after hatching at larva stage. CFP signals can be observed in fin muscles, head muscles but mainly in skeletal muscles. After yolk sac absorption was completed, larva activity was increased. At this stage, the swimming movement was mainly powered by muscle of pectoral fin. At 8 days post hatching, muscles of dorsal, pelvic and anal fin started to develop indicating the change of swimming propulsion from anterior powered propulsion (using pectoral fin) to posterior powered propulsion (using dorsal and caudal fin). At 20 days post hatching, fin muscle, head muscle are completely developed. During post flexion stage, all fin rays are undergoing development. Pelvic fin rays and pectoral fin rays are the last fin rays that will complete development before larva enter the juvenile stage (Gao *et al.*, 2014).

IV. CONCLUSION

This study describes the molecular characterization of the *mlc2f* gene from mud loach (*Misgurnus mizolepis*). From an experimental transgenesis experiment using the cyan fluorescent protein reporter construct under the control by the mud loach *mlc2f* promoter, the *mlc2f* regulator was proven to be highly functional to drive skeletal muscle-dominant expression of the foreign protein in transgenic fish. A stable transgenic line was generated with germ line transmission testing.

The level of mRNA expression was the highest in skeletal muscle compared to other tissues. CFP signals were reliably expressed throughout the life cycle of mud loach. Expression pattern of CFP is parallel with the pattern of endogenous *mlc2f*. Strong expression of CFP in skeletal muscle indicated the main function of myosin for muscle contraction during body lateral muscle undulation which are the main propulsive force in the fish.

CFP expression in skeletal muscles especially in caudal peduncle and base of caudal fin signifies the importance of posterior body as the main apparatus for generating underwater swimming movement and thrust in mud loach.

These results could provide the foundation of *mlc2f* promoter to drive expression of foreign protein in skeletal muscle of mud loach. Stable and uniform expression of vivid cyan fluorescent protein in skeletal muscle suggests the potential of loach as ornamental fish. Also, strong expression of CFP in skeletal muscle could prove beneficial as a bioreactor platform for the production of foreign protein in transgenic loach.

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VII. ABSTRACT (Korean)

미꾸라지(*Misgurnus mizolepis*)로부터 *mhc2f* 유전자의 분리 및 형질전환 시스템을 이용한 발현특징 분석)

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요약

미꾸라지(*Misgurnus mizolepis*)로부터 골격근 myosin light chain2 (*mhc2f*) 유전자를 분리하고 분자적 특성을 분석하였다. Wild 타입의 성체 미꾸라지에서 *mhc2f* mRNA 발현은 골격근에서 우월적으로 높게 나타난 반면 피부 및 아가미에서는 상대적으로 매우 낮은 것으로 나타났다. 위 특징을 바탕으로 골격근 특이적 발현을 유도하는 미꾸라지 *mhc2f* 유전자의 프로모터 영역과 cyan 형광 단백질 발현 유전자를 reporter로 사용하여 형질전환 미꾸라지 개발용 발현 벡터를 구축하였다. 미세현미주입 기법으로 발현 벡터를 수정란에 주입하여 모자이크 패턴의 현상을 지닌 F0 형광 발현 미꾸라지를 확보하였다. 수컷 형광 미꾸라지 F0와 wild 타입의 암컷 미꾸라지의 교배를 통하여 세대전달 가능 여부 확인을 하였다. 형질전환 미꾸라지의 F1 개체의 형광 발현 특징은 난 발생 과정 중에 형광 발현이 나타나지 않은 점으로서 처음 cyan 형광 단백질 발현은 부화 후 12시간 췌인 것으로 확인되었다. 형질전환 미꾸라지의 자어 단계에서 형광 발현은 지느러미 근육, 머리 근육 및 골격 근육에서 나타났고, 치어 단계에서는 형광 발현 부위가 넓어지는 현상이 관찰되었으며 성장 발달이 진행됨에 따라 형광 발현이 점차 강해지는 패턴을 보였다. 형질전환 미꾸라지 내 형광 단백질 유전자와 *mhc2f* 유전자의 조직별 전사발현 특징 분석을 수행한 결과 다른 조직에 비하여 근육에서 우월적으로 높은 발현을 나타내었다. 또한 형질전환 미꾸라지 F2 세대의 확보를 통하여 안정적 유전자 전달 및 멘델 유전 법칙을 따르는 것으로 확인되었다. 본 연구를 통하여 골격근 특이적 발현을 유도하는 미꾸라지 *mhc2f* 유전자의 프로모터 기능을 형광 단백질 발현 패턴을 통하여 확인하였고, 성장단계별 근육 내 myosin 단백질 발달을 확인하였다.